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Research Article

**ASSOCIATION BETWEEN NEURAL TUBE DEFECTS AND
DEFICIENCY OF SERUM COPPER**

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Article Received: April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

Objectives: This research work carried out to find out the relationship between concentration of the serum copper and NTD (Neural Tube Defects) pregnancies in our region which is stated as a high prevalence region for NTDs.

Methodology: This is a case control research work carried out on thirteen mothers with neonates present with NTDs and thirty-five mothers as healthy controls from the same region in the duration of June 2018 to November 2019. Spectrophotometer was in use for the measurement of copper in serum.

Results: The level of serum copper in females present with newborns with NTDs and females with healthy neonates was 15.90 ± 6.10 micro-mol per liter and 15.20 ± 6.20 micro-mol per liter, correspondingly. Overall, 15.40% females in case-group and 25.70 % females in the group of healthy controls were present with deficiency of copper. Logistic regression analysis stated no relationship between the deficiency of copper and NTDs presence (OR= 0.50, 95.0% CI: 0.050-3.20).

Conclusion: The findings of this research work declared that there is no relation between the level of concentration of copper in serum and presence of NTDs (Neural Tube Defects).

KEY WORDS: NTDs, serum, copper, deficiency, regression, analysis, controls, case-group, prevalence, measurement, pregnancy.

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INTRODUCTION:

NTD are the most important reason of high rate of mortality among infants and high rate of morbidity in childhood period [1, 2]. There are many factors being considered in etiology of NTDs, nutritional, environmental and genetic factors are playing important roles [3-5]. Many research works have discovered a high prevalence of NTDs in our country, Pakistan. The occurrence of NTDs is present in approximately 28 to 32 per ten thousand births in Pakistan [6, 7]. These rates of prevalence are much high as compared to prevalence rate of NTDs in USA (9.30-14.60 per 10000) [8] and England (17.90 per 10000) [9] & France [10]. The results of different research work discovered that supplementation of the folic acid before conception and in period of early pregnancy reduced the prevalence of NTDs greater than fifty percent [11, 12]. There are some proofs that the prevalence of NTDs can be decreased even further by large supplementation of folic acid, there may be some other factors of environment, possibly nutritional, that participate to the NTD's etiology, because supplementation of folic acid and protection with folic acid have not eradicated all neural tube defects [13].

There is inconsistent information regarding the association between the level of serum copper in mothers and incidence of NTDs. Some research work displayed that exposure to the copper sulfate caused the failure in the increase of neural folds and lead to the development of NTDs in the mouse embryo [14] and copper-bearing intra-uterine devices were correlated with the anencephaly in anecdotal patients [15]. One other research work showed that there is a strong association between the high copper concentration in the pregnancy period and NTD presence in neonates [13]. Some research work concluded that deficiency of copper was present with association to teratogenesis [16, 17].

Copper plays very important role in the development of embryo and deficiency of copper in the period of embryogenesis can be the reason of NTDs. The reasons of deficiency of copper can be because of the decrease in the activity of enzymes and rise in the amount of oxidative damages [18, 19]. Buamah [17] stated that that concentration of serum copper was much low in abnormal pregnancies. Bro stated that there is no relationship between the deficiency of copper in pregnancy period and presence of NTDs in neonates [20]. This research work carried out to

determine the relationship between level of serum copper and NTDs in our regions.

METHODOLOGY:

This case-control research work started in June 2018 and lasted up to November 2019 at Mayo Hospital, Lahore. Ethical committee of the institute gave the permission to conduct this research work. There were total thirteen mothers having newborns with NTD and control group consisted thirty-five females having healthy babies. We selected all these participants from the delivery list of the department. Control were higher in number as compared to cases. We took the consent of the mothers after explaining them the purpose of this research work. The collection of the data carried out about maternal age, exposure to medicines in the period of pregnancy and parity number. Gynecologist diagnosed the health and NTD after the delivery and pediatrician confirmed the diagnosis after that.

The collection of the specimens of peripheral blood carried out from both control and case groups within two hours after the delivery. The separation of the serum carried out and spectrophotometric procedure was in use for the analysis of the level of copper in serum, utilizing the Randox Kit UR21 level of copper from 12.0 to 24.40 micro-mol per liter was considered as normal. Level of serum copper lower than twelve micro-mol per liter was utilized as cutoff to label the participant as copper-deficient.

Fisher exact test was in use for the comparison of the categorical data. The availability of the NTD was thought as dependent factor in analysis of logistics regression. Parity number, drug exposure and past history of abortions were the independent variables. SPSS V. 20 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. P value of less than 0.050 was significant one.

RESULTS:

Baseline traits of the participants are present in Table-1. Level of serum copper (Average $\pm$ Standard Deviation) in mothers with NTDs affected babies and females having healthy neonates was 15.90 ± 6.10 micro-mol per liter and 15.20 ± 6.20 micro-mol per liter, correspondingly. Overall, 15.40% females in the case-group and 25.70 females in the group of healthy controls were present with deficiency of copper. Logistic regression analysis concluded no relationship between the deficiency of copper and availability of NTDs (OR= 0.50, 95.0% CI: 0.050-3.20).

Table-I: Maternal characteristics in both groups

Characteristics	Cases (n=13)		Controls (n=35)		P-value
	No	Percent	No	Percent	
Maternal age: year	24.30	5.80	25.40	5.00	0.5600
Paternal age: year	26.50	79.90	27.90	4.70	0.1300
Gestational age: week	34.70	5.30	38.10	1.50	0.0480
Drug Use (%)	2.00	15.40	2.00	5.70	0.2940

DISCUSSION:

This research work showed that there is no relationship between the deficiency of copper and NTD. This finding is similar with the outcome of the research works conducted by Bro in Denmark [20] and McMichael [22] in Australia. McMichael in his research work conducted in Australia concluded that there is no correlation between deficiency of copper and NTDs. Bro in his research work conducted in Denmark also reported that there is no association between concentration of copper level and NTD. Opposite to the similar findings, our results are not consistent with the outcomes of other research work conducted by Cengiz in Turkey [13], Buamah in UK [17] and Morton in South Wales [23]. Buamah from UK stated that the concentration of copper in serum among mothers are meaningfully less in period of pregnancies with anencephaly or abortions.

Morton in his research work conducted in South Wales [23] stated that there is no correlation between maternal deficiency of copper and availability of NTD among neonates. In opposition with the research work of Buamah & Morton research studies [17, 23], Cengiz from Turkey [13] concluded that level of serum copper among mothers was significantly higher in the period of pregnancies with anencephaly in comparison with healthy controls. O'shea & Kufman [14] stated that

acquaintance to copper sulfate normally caused in failure of advancement of neural folds and leads to the development of neural tube defects in the mouse embryos.

Saner & Yuksel in their research work [24] stated that maternal level of serum copper were significantly high in the pregnancies with NTD as compared to healthy controls in which there is very low level of serum Zn. One other research work conducted in past [25] showed that mothers present with the newborn suffering from NTDs always had deficiency of zinc as compared to the females having healthy babies, but in current research work, we did not calculate the level of serum zinc but one possible mechanism can be associated to the interaction of zinc-copper during absorption in intestines which could be the reply for relative rise in copper among patients present with neural tube defects in our participants.

Mechanism of Zn's anti-copper action is distinctive, it encourages intestinal cell metallothionein, which has the ability to binds copper and restricts the transfer of copper in blood supply. As there is death and slough of the intestinal cells, the elimination of the contained copper carried out through stool. Thus, Zn restricts the absorption of copper in the intestines [26]. An increased absorption in females with Zn

deficiency may be accountable for enhanced levels of copper, as stated by some other small research works. There are some limitations of this research work as the sample size of this research work was much low. Therefore, it is need to conduct research work on large sample size for the evaluation of the association between level of serum copper and zinc with neonatal outcome.

CONCLUSION:

Regardless of the mentioned limitations of this research work, the results of this research work concluded that there is no association between level of copper in mothers and NTDs.

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